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Forest species mapping and area proportion estimation combining Sentinel-2 harmonic predictors and national forest inventory data

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ABSTRACT

European forest monitoring is a central topic nowadays due to the critical role that forests can play in combatting climate change. Crucial information on forests is the number of tree species and the area covered by each of them, as they vary concerning growth rates, wood value, value for biodiversity conservation, and susceptibility to disturbances and global warming. The primary source of forest information is national forest inventories (NFIs). However, they are updated too infrequently to accommodate climate change-related analyses, and their estimates are not based on wall-to-wall information. Remotely sensed data offer new opportunities for up-to-date and large-scale forest monitoring and for enhancing NFI estimates. However, despite the huge scientific efforts, it is still challenging to accurately map forest species through satellite imagery analysis.

This study introduces a method for large-scale forest species mapping in the Netherlands using Sentinel-2 (S2) *harmonic predictors* and demonstrates a scientific procedure for reliably estimating area proportions from remote sensing-based species maps and comparing these estimates with NFI-based estimates.

Compared to more standard predictors, *harmonic predictors* increased the model performance by 8% in terms of overall accuracy and the kappa coefficient by 9% while reducing omission and commission errors by as much as 18% and 13%, respectively. We estimated the area proportion of forest species for each 10-km cell covering the Netherlands first using NFI data and then using the predicted maps. Although the resulting estimates differ by source data and methods, we found an average deviation between NFI and remote sensing-based area proportion estimates of 9%, with deviations approaching 0% when increasing the number of NFI plots per cell.

The outcomes of this research play an important role in understanding the relative strengths and limitations of remote sensing-based products and NFI data, as well as be a solid basis for forest species area proportion estimation when (i) no field data are available, (ii) more frequently updated estimates are required, or (iii) wall-to-wall and fine resolution spatially explicit estimates are needed.

1. Introduction

Forests are a strategic resource, sequestering carbon from the atmosphere and providing biodiversity protection, building materials, firewood, and recreation. To regulate forest use and prevent over-exploitation, forest owners and communities have introduced methods for planning and regulation (Gabler and Schadauer, 2007; Loetsch and

Haller, 1973). National Forest Inventories (NFIs) historically provide critical information on forest resources (Schelhaas et al., 2014; Schelhaas et al., 2022). NFIs collect reliable information on the ground designed to provide statistically rigorous estimates at the regional and national levels. However, this information is collected at small densities – 1 sample plot per 100–1000 ha, depending on the sampling design – and with generally long – 5–12 years – time intervals (Tomppo et al.,

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2010). Large owners like State Forest Services often apply similar methods with greater sampling densities, while smaller owners usually lack the knowledge and financial means to collect information on their properties. Historically, NFIs have addressed the inquiry “How much?” by providing plot-based estimates of forest species area proportions, but users are nowadays inquiring “Where?”. In this context, NFIs can serve not only to present tabular estimates but also – in combination with remotely sensed data – generate maps illustrating the geographical distribution of forest resources (McRoberts and Tomppo, 2007).

In contrast to NFIs, satellites collect wall-to-wall data frequently and with fine spatial detail. The complementarity of these methods has long been recognized, and many studies have explored possibilities for integration (e.g., Tomppo et al., 2008). The recent combination of open-access remotely sensed data (Wulder et al., 2019; Wulder et al., 2012) with cloud computing platforms (Gorelick et al., 2017) further increase the possibilities in this area of research by facilitating application of complex algorithms over entire countries and long study periods (Francini et al., 2023a). Still, remote sensing applications were for a long time limited to forest cover and area (Schuck et al., 2002; Cavalli et al., 2022; D’Amico et al., 2021; Francini et al., 2023b) and forest disturbance assessments (Hansen et al., 2013; Hermosilla et al., 2015a; Francini et al., 2021; Francini et al., 2022b; 2022c; Francini et al., 2020; Palahi et al., 2021). The integration of remotely sensed data with ground surveys has facilitated construction of spatially explicit maps of multiple variables of interest (Liu et al., 2017; Oreja et al., 2015; Braaten et al., 2018; Francini et al., 2022a; Hawrylo et al., 2020). However, an essential variable in forest inventories, forest species area proportions, is still very difficult to accurately predict using Landsat or similar medium-resolution data (Hermosilla et al., 2022). Several key aspects of forests depend on tree species, including growth rates (Schelhaas et al., 2018), wood value, value for biodiversity conservation (Branquart and Liégeois, 2010), susceptibility to disturbances, water usage, applicable management types, and fire behavior (Cansler et al., 2020). Also, tree species choice is key in the current era of changing climate conditions and one of the major decisions in forest management (Duncker et al., 2012), with the effects lasting beyond the forest manager’s lifetime.

Large-scale and accurate classification of remotely sensed data with respect to tree species beyond the distinction between broadleaves and conifers remained a main challenge for a long time, even with the relatively limited number of dominant species in Europe. In addition – as part of the transition towards more close-to-nature forest management – many European countries are transforming monospecific plantations into heterogeneous mixed-species stands (Larsen et al., 2022), which makes species area proportion assessment even more difficult. In this framework, remote sensing faced new challenges because of the large variety of management styles, from high forest to coppice, old and young forests, mixed and monospecies forests, an increasing variety of species, and stand size classes. Large-scale tree species mapping based on optical satellite imagery was for a long time limited to distinguishing between conifers and broadleaves based primarily on differences in the reflectance of the infrared wavelength (Larsen, 2007; Warner et al., 2009). While some studies demonstrated that it is possible to predict forest species using airborne laser scanning data with substantial point densities, such data are usually available over small areas and rarely updated.

Consequently, related studies covered only limited areas (hundreds of km²), and are not suitable for country-level implementations and national estimate reporting. As a result, the step from local to large scale remains one of the biggest challenges in tree species mapping through remote sensing (Fassnacht et al. 2016).

With Sentinel-2 (S2), data became available at a sufficient spatial and temporal resolution to start addressing this gap. Plakman et al. (2020) demonstrated the usefulness of coupling S2 and lidar data in this respect by mapping eight tree species in a temperate forest, reaching an accuracy of 78.5%. On the other hand, upscaling to large areas decreases the mapping accuracy as it increases the heterogeneity in the spectral

signal from the same forest species due to the greater variability in environmental conditions and management (Hemmerling et al., 2021). This emphasizes the importance of predictor consistency and model generalizability. The recent study by Hemmerling et al. (2021) using S2 data which focused on a study area of 30,000 km² was groundbreaking in this sense, showing a per-class accuracy between 66.8% and 98.9% for the main tree species.

One major problem in large areas is the data gap caused by cloud coverage (White et al., 2014, Francini et al., 2023a). In areas characterized by consistent cloud cover, composites spanning a few days would not be sufficient to construct consistent predictors. On the other hand, data acquired over more years could lead to misclassification and inaccuracy due to changes on the ground that can occur over a long period. For large-scale species mapping, inter-annual differences in phenological behavior should be sought, exploiting the short revisit time of the S2 mission. Critically, balanced datasets in which all species are approximately equally represented are needed to obtain performant classification models, reliable maps, and reliable model performance assessments (Hermosilla et al., 2022). More explicit and more transparent map validation remains indeed a major challenge in remote sensing of forests as a result of the capability of using remote sensing-based maps to estimate forest species area proportions for specific regions of interest (Vangi et al., 2021). Comparing per-pixel predictions obtained through remote sensing and NFI data is challenging for several reasons. First, the spatial resolution of pixels is usually too coarse to properly compare pixel predictions and ground data, because a pixel may only partially overlap the ground plot. Also, imprecision associated with inaccurate ground plot coordinates can amplify this issue. Second, multiple forest species are often found within a single ground plot, while a pixel is usually classified with a single label to produce categorical maps. Consequently, the model predictions based on remotely sensed data for single pixels can be inaccurate (McRoberts and Tomppo, 2007). Historically, these issues adversely affect the utility of combined NFI and remotely sensed data, training forest species prediction models, and understanding the quality of the resulting remote sensing-based maps and estimates.

This study focuses on the Netherlands and demonstrates a method for large-scale tree species mapping using an S2 time series. Specifically, we compared forest species map accuracies obtained using time series-derived *harmonic predictors* to accuracies obtained using standard seasonal composites. Secondly, we demonstrated a method for obtaining reliable estimates of forest species area proportions from remote sensing-based species maps and compared these estimates with NFI-based estimates. The study focused on two objectives: (i) to assess the degree to which *harmonic predictors*, balanced reference datasets, and the herein presented procedure can improve the performance of large scale forest species mapping, and (ii) to compare small area estimates of forest species area proportions obtained using remote sensing with official NFI estimates. large-scale

2. Study area

This study focuses on Netherlands forests delineated using a 25-meter resolution forest mask obtained from the 2017 land use map (Fig. 1) produced for annual greenhouse gas reporting (Arets et al., 2022) and used as a basis for the NFI. According to these data, the forest area proportion in the Netherlands is about 11% or 370,000 ha. Forests have a diverse species distribution linked to differences in forest history, site conditions, and changes in species preferences over time. Although the Dutch forest area is small in the European context, forests are important for Dutch society. The most common species is Scots pine (*Pinus sylvestris*, 28%), which was planted at a large scale in the period 1900–1960 to restore degraded land, along with smaller areas of Corsican and Austrian pine (*Pinus nigra*, 4%). Areas with slightly better soils were planted with non-native conifers such as Larch (*Larix decidua*, 5%), Norway spruce (*Picea abies*, 3%), and Douglas fir (*Pseudotsuga*

Fig. 1. Landuse in the Netherlands in 2017 according to Arets et al. (2022).

menziesii, 5%) (Schelhaas et al., 2022). Also, old oak and beech mixed forest remnants persist on relatively poor soils. Forest area expansion in the second half of the 20th century featured mostly broadleaved species. A large part of this area expansion has been realized on richer soils in the land reclamation area of the Flevopolder, including large poplar plantations, but also sizeable proportions of beech, ash, and oak. The most important broadleaved species are native oak (18%), birch (6%), and beech (4%), while other species have shares of 1–3%. Since the late 1980s, greater attention has been paid to promoting the admixture of native broadleaved species in these stands and increasing the structural diversity. As a result, subsequent inventories show a slow but steady increase in the proportion of broadleaved species over time (about 50% in NFI-7), an increased area of forest classified as uneven-aged (from 13% in NFI-5 to 22% in NFI-7), and a decreased proportion of mono-species coniferous forests (from 39% in NFI-5 to 20% in NFI-7).

3. Data

3.1. S2 data

In this study, we used S2 surface reflectance level 2 data available in the Google Earth Engine GEE archive (Gorelick et al., 2017), from which we selected all images acquired over the Netherlands between 2019–09–01 and 2020–08–31 with less than 50% cloud cover (White et al., 2014), for a total of 4149 images. Clouds were masked out using the S2 cloud probability dataset (Shi et al., 2022) and by masking out pixels with a cloud cover probability of 65% or more (Parisi et al., 2023; Bozzini et al., 2023).

3.2. National forest inventory data

The Dutch NFI design consists of a semi-regular grid over the country with one sample plot per 100 ha. Sample plots are circular with a variable radius, such that at least 20 trees are included, limited to a range of 5–20 m. All trees on the sample plot are calibrated, and their species are

recorded as well as their status (alive, dead standing, or dead lying). In addition, other qualitative characteristics of the stand are recorded including the size class (<0.1 ha, 01–0.5 ha, >0.5 ha), the main species, and the crown coverage of the tree and the shrub layer. The actual plot coordinates may deviate slightly (maximum 20 m) from the coordinates as given by the original grid map, due to inaccuracies in the GPS systems used when the sample plots were established in the field. For this study, we extracted data acquired in 2012 and 2013 within NFI-6 (Schelhaas et al., 2014) from the online database (www.probos.nl/publicaties/overige/1094-mfv-2006-nbi-2012, produced on 2 September 2016), amended with plot coordinates.

4. Method

4.1. S2 predictors

4.1.1. Indices calculation

For each S2 image (section 3.1), we increased the number of available predictors by expanding the original bands (blue, green, red, redE1, redE2, redE3, nir, redE4, swir1, swir2) with seven additional spectral indices: (i) Normalized Difference Vegetation Index (NDVI), (ii) Normalized Burned Ratio (NBR), (iii) Enhanced Vegetation Index (EVI), (iv) Tasseled Cap Brightness (TCB), (v) Tasseled Cap Wetness (TCW), (vi) Tasseled Cap Greenness (TCG), and Tasseled Cap Angle (TCA) (Parisi et al., 2023). As a result of our index calculations, we obtained for each image (section 3.1) a 10-m resolution stack of 17 bands: the 10 S2 bands, and the seven indices.

4.1.2. Harmonic predictors calculation

The development of remote sensing-based methods suitable for country-wide applicability requires consistent, cloud-free input data over the whole study area. Multiple methods are available for constructing pixel-based image composites and for producing a single image approximation of the whole study area under ideal atmospheric conditions (White et al., 2014; Kennedy et al., 2018). Such composites are constructed by combining pixel values from several images based on given compositing rules (Francini et al., 2023). Most of these methods – e.g. BAP (Hermosilla et al., 2018) and Medoid – aim to construct seasonal composites, or images that approximate the pixels' reflectances within a defined season. However, to predict forest species using S2 time series, it is crucial to obtain cloud-free composites that provide wall-to-wall and consistent information on the phenology, i.e., on the temporal per-pixel spectral behavior. To this end, we fitted a harmonic function for each pixel time series and each of the 17 bands in our images. While a linear function is defined using two coefficients, the harmonic function is defined by four coefficients: β_0 is the constant, β_1 is the time coefficient, and β_2 and β_3 are the frequency sine and cosine coefficients, respectively. To fit these four coefficients and to select p_t , the pixel p harmonic values at time t , we used a least squares regression to fit Eq. (1) (Shumway and Stoffer, 2017).

$$p_t = \beta_0 + \beta_1 t + A \cos(2\pi\omega t - \varphi) = \beta_0 + \beta_1 t + \beta_2 \cos(2\pi\omega t) + \beta_3 \sin(2\pi\omega t) \quad (1)$$

where $\omega = 1$ (in years) is the frequency and indicates one cycle per unit of time, $\beta_2 = A \cos(\varphi)$, and $\beta_3 = A \sin(\varphi)$, implying $A = (\beta_2^2 + \beta_3^2)^{1/2}$ and $\varphi = \text{atan}(\beta_3/\beta_2)$, where A is the amplitude or the translation of the harmonic curve on the y-axis, and φ is the phase or the translation of the curve on the x-axis to the origin. Shumway and Stoffer (2017, equations 4.1–4.2) provide more details on *harmonic predictors* calculations from vector time series. Finally, we further calculated the Root Mean Square Error (RMSE) between p_t (blue dots in Fig. 2) and the actual pixel values (red dots in Fig. 2).

As a result of the calculation of the seven harmonic metrics (β_0 , β_1 , β_2 , β_3 , A , φ , and RMSE) for each of the 17 S2 bands, we obtained a set of 119 predictors, hereafter characterized as *harmonic predictors*.

Fig. 2. Example of harmonic function (blue line) fitted on observed NDVI time-series (red dots). The green segments show phase and amplitude. (For interpretation of the references to colour in this figure legend, the reader is referred to the web version of this article.)

4.1.3. Medoid predictors

To evaluate the advantages of *harmonic predictors*, we calculated cloud-free composite predictors as a benchmark. More specifically, we calculated four seasonal cloud-free composites: (i) autumn composite – using images acquired between 2019–09-01 and 2019–11-30 – (ii) winter composite – using images acquired between 2019–12-01 and 2020–02-28 – (iii) spring composite, using images acquired between 2020–03-01 and 2020–05-31 – and (iv) summer composite – using images acquired between 2020–06-01 and 2020–08-31. To calculate those cloud-free composites, we used the state-of-the-science methodology, *Medoid* (Kennedy et al., 2018). The Medoid pixel compositing algorithm aims to populate the final image with pixels whose surface reflectance values are as similar as possible to the median calculated considering the entire image collection.

For each season, the band’s pixel values are compared with the median calculated considering all images available using Euclidean distance, and the spectral values from the pixel with the smallest Euclidean distance to the median are selected (Francini et al., 2023a; Kennedy et al., 2018; Flood, 2013). This process resulted in four seasonal Medoid composites for each of 17 bands for a total of 68 predictors, hereafter characterized as *medoid predictors*.

4.2. Random forest modeling

Random forests (RF) is a widely embraced decision trees-based, machine-learning model (Breiman, 2001). Using RF, each decision tree within the ‘forest’ is constructed using distinct training subsets and predictors. These subsets are generated by bootstrapping the initial training dataset and using a random subset of predictors at each node for splitting, aiming to mitigate correlation among trees. RF, indeed, effectively mitigates output variance and overfitting issues, and enhances model stability and accuracy, thereby distinguishing itself from alternative machine learning methodologies. RF stands as a firmly established technique and a popular choice in remote sensing of forestry applications (McRoberts et al., 2023; Hermosilla et al., 2022). In this study, we exploited the randomForest R package to train the RF models, using the default RF hyperparameters: ntree was set to 500 and mtry to the square of the number of predictors (Breiman, 2002).

4.2.1. Reference data balancing

For training purposes, NFI plot data including tree species must be adequately linked to the spectral signal registered by S2. To do so, sources of confusion between the information remote sensing provides

on tree species and the information acquired on the ground within NFIs must be limited. Species observed on the plot may deviate from the main species of the stand due to the presence of groups of admixed species. We, therefore, limited our selection to plots whose main recorded forest species had basal area proportions equal to or greater than 80% and were the same as the main species of the stand as a whole. This resulted in a set of 1398 sample plots with suitable training data. We then aggregated species into seven groups based on their assumed similarities in phenology and structure, their proportion of the country total, and their importance for forest managers in terms of wood production and biodiversity protection, and we assigned each group to either the broadleaves or conifers category (Table 1). The 80% threshold is used in the Netherlands NFI to define monocultures and is a common threshold in forest inventories (Schelhaas et al., 2014).

To increase the reliability of the training dataset, we photo-interpreted the 1398 plots using S2 images, Google satellite images, and orthophotos. In particular, we removed points that had experienced land cover change (harvesting), fell outside the available forest mask, or were too mixed to distinguish a particular species group. To increase the reference data for training and validation of the model, we identified stand borders around the remaining plots by visually identifying homogeneous areas, obtaining a dataset of 882 stand polygons containing 348,545 S2 pixels (10x10 m). Finally, we reduced issues associated with spatial autocorrelation by removing adjacent pixels from the reference dataset – the minimum distance among sample pixels was set to 15 m (Hermosilla et al., 2022). As a result of this step, we obtained a dataset of

Table 1
Species registered in the reference data.

Species	Species group	Category	Data availability (%)
Pinus sylvestris, Pinus nigra nigra, Pinus nigra maritima	Pinus	Conifers	56.8
Larix decidua, Larix kampfieri	Larix	Conifers	1.6
Picea abies, Pseudotsuga menziesii, and other conifers	Dark conifer	Conifers	6.3
Quercus robur, Quercus petraea	Quercus	Broadleaves	13.1
Fagus sylvatica	Beech	Broadleaves	1.5
Populus spp.	Populus	Broadleaves	2.7
Betula spp., Quercus rubra, Acer spp., Alnus spp., Fraxinus spp., Salix spp., other broadleaves	Other broadleaves	Broadleaves	18.0

134,427 pixels distributed in the seven species groups as shown in the data availability column of Table 1. The very unbalanced distribution of such pixels in the seven species groups is in line with the overall species coverage as described in section 2. Unbalanced reference datasets are a well-known issue when constructing models and when assessing their performance (Kumar et al., 2021). To overcome this issue, we equalized the sample by randomly selecting pixels from all species groups such that the sample size per species group was equal to the sample size of the species group with the fewest observations (1,970 pixels for *Fagus*). Our final dataset, therefore, consisted of a set of 1,970 pixels for each of the seven species groups, for a total of 13,790 pixels.

4.2.2. Training

Using the balanced reference data (Section 4.2.1), we used RF to predict the seven species groups and the two forest categories (table 1). Each of these two classification tasks was performed using three different sets of predictors: (i) *harmonic predictors*, (ii) *medoid predictors*, and (iii) both *harmonic* and *medoid predictors*. As a result, six models were constructed.

4.2.3. Predictors importance assessment

We examined the importance of the predictor variables for all six models using the Mean Decrease in Accuracy (MDA) produced by the RF model. MDA is a fundamental outcome of RF, and by expressing the model accuracy lost when excluding each variable, the importance of each variable for the classification task can be estimated. The greater the decrease in accuracy, the greater the influence of the variable for successful classification (Breiman, 2001).

4.2.4. Validation and implementation

We expressed the performance of each of the six models using the out-of-bag (OOB) error estimate. The OOB samples consist of data points not included in the bootstrap sample used to train a particular tree. These OOB sample units act as a validation set for each RF decision tree (Hastie et al., 2009). The OOB error is calculated by aggregating the predictions made by each tree on its corresponding OOB sample units. OOB error estimates the model's performance without the need for a separate validation set and produces precise accuracy estimates (Breiman, 2001). Because adjacent pixels were removed from our reference dataset, issues associated with auto-correlation were addressed and the OOB error is an independent estimate of model performance.

In summary, during RF training, two independent sets are created for each decision tree: (i) the bootstrap sample, i.e., the data chosen to be "in-the-bag" by sampling with replacement, and (ii) the OOB sample, i.e., all data not chosen in the sampling process. Because OOB samples are not used to train decision trees, they can be used independently to assess the model's performance. More specifically, OOB predictions are aggregated and compared with reference data by constructing a confusion matrix. Using that confusion matrix, we assessed the performance of each of the six models in terms of (i) overall accuracy *OA*, (ii) Cohen coefficient *kappa*, (iii) *omission* errors, and (iv) *commission* errors. Although *kappa* may provide misleading information on map accuracy (Foody, 2020), it is a well-known valuable indicator of model performance. Then, a *forest species map* for the Netherlands was constructed using the model with the greatest values of the performance measures. Finally, we estimated the overall and the per-class accuracies of the resulting map and the related 95% confidence intervals using the procedure detailed by Olofsson et al. (2014) and implemented using the calculation shown in Table B.6.

4.3. Comparing NFI and remote sensing estimates

Comparing per-pixel predictions and ground or NFI data can be challenging for several reasons. First, the spatial resolution of pixels is usually too fine to properly compare remote sensing and ground data because, as previously noted, a pixel may only partially overlap with the

ground plot and the plot coordinates can be affected by geolocation errors. Second, the model predictions based on the remotely sensed data can be inaccurate for individual pixels (McRoberts and Tomppo, 2007). Third, and more critically, multiple forest species are often found on a single ground plot, while a pixel is classified with a single label to produce categorical forest species maps.

To address these issues and to compare NFI and remote sensing-based estimates of forest species area proportions, we tessellated the Netherlands into a 10x10 km grid, resulting in a total of 452 cells. Blackard et al. (2008) used a similar approach to assess the accuracy of a US-wide biomass map. We calculated remote sensing-based estimates of forest species area proportions as the proportions of the per-pixel predictions within each grid cell. For example, if a cell with 30% of pixels classified as *dark conifer* and 70% of pixels classified as *pinus*, the cell will be predicted to be covered by just these two forest species groups: 30% of the cell area will be *dark conifers* and 70% will be *pinus*. A two-step procedure was used to calculate NFI-based estimates comparable to those predicted by remote sensing. First, we calculated the basal area proportion of each species group for each NFI plot. Second, we calculated the NFI-based species distribution for each cell as the average of basal area proportions considering all plots in the cell. This metric produced the NFI-based estimates of forest species area proportions which are similar to the proportions from the forest species map in that they consider the actual mixture in a plot or stand rather than allocating the entire area to a single dominant species. Finally, for each cell, we calculated the *deviation* as the difference between the forest species area proportions predicted using remote sensing and those based on basal areas for NFI plots (Fig. 3).

5. Results

In Figs. 4-6, we show the performance of the six models in terms of *OA*, *kappa*, *omissions*, and *commissions*, while the respective confusion matrices are in Appendix B. The models with the greatest accuracies used all predictors, followed by models using just *harmonic predictors*, and lastly, models using just *medoid predictors*. Considering models classifying species groups (Fig. 4, bottom), *harmonic predictors*, compared to *medoid predictors*, increased the overall accuracy from 73.9% to 81.2% and *kappa* from 69.5% to 78.1%. Considering models predicting coniferous and broadleaf categories (Fig. 4, top), the advantage of *harmonic predictors* was confirmed but smaller: the overall accuracy increased from 90.5% to 91.9% and *kappa* from 80.6% to 83.3%.

The greater accuracies of models using *harmonic predictors* relative to the accuracies of models using *medoid predictors* were confirmed by considering *omissions* (Fig. 5) and *commissions* (Fig. 6). The most substantial difference in omissions and commissions between *harmonic* and *medoid predictors* was for the *Larix* species group. *Larix omissions* and *commissions* using *harmonic predictors* were 14.2% and 17.3%, while using *medoid predictors*, they were 31.5% and 30.1% respectively. *Medoid predictors* even adversely affected the accuracy in some cases (*Larix omissions* and *commissions*, *Other broadleaves omissions*, *Quercus commissions*, and *Fagus commissions*) as the model's accuracy using just *harmonic predictors* was greater than the accuracy when using both *harmonic predictors* and *medoid predictors*.

The *forest species map* of the seven species groups was produced for the whole of the Netherlands using the most performant model, i.e., exploiting both *harmonic* and *medoid predictors*. The resulting map is shown in Fig. 7 while map accuracy estimates with 95% confidence intervals are shown in Table 2.

The average per-cell deviation between the remote sensing-based and NFI-based estimates of forest species area proportion was 9% (Fig. 8), and ranged between 0.2% for Oaks and 23% for *Other broadleaves*. Considering just cells with at least 10 plots, the average deviation was 7.5% while considering just cells with at least 20 plots, the average deviation was 6% and no greater than 10% for any species. This means that remote sensing-based estimates were very similar to estimates

Fig. 3. Schematic representation of the procedure we implemented to compare NFI and remote sensing-based estimates of per-cell forest species area proportions.

Fig. 4. The OA and Kappa coefficients of models classifying coniferous and broadleaf (top) and species groups (bottom) using *medoid predictors* (green), *harmonic predictors* (red), and all predictors (blue). (For interpretation of the references to colour in this figure legend, the reader is referred to the web version of this article.)

obtained using ground data when considered over large enough areas and aggregating a sufficient number of pixels and NFI plots.

The agreement between remote sensing-based and NFI-based estimates was substantial (Fig. 9). Smaller correlations were recorded for less represented species, suggesting that the number of NFI plots was too small for those species to provide reliable estimates. Accordingly, *Fagus*

and *Larix* were the least represented species groups (Table 1) and, indeed, in Fig. 9 they have the yellowest dots and the smallest correlations between RS and NFI estimates.

6. Discussion

6.1. Contextualization of the study

European policies currently focus on forest-based climate change mitigation and adaptation strategies, thereby making it key to monitor species distribution across the continent and provide reliable national estimates over time. Such estimates are usually provided by NFIs, which collect data at small densities and long time intervals (5–12 years), a crucial limitation for promptly responding to rapid global warming. Forest species mapping via analysis of satellite imagery is a historical challenge for the remote sensing community. While several attempts have been made over time, several limitations remain, mainly related to small or very unbalanced per-class accuracies, difficulties in upscaling the products, and lack of statistically rigorous integration with available reference data. Most importantly, the integration of remotely sensed data with NFI data to produce reliable and up-to-date maps and estimates holds dramatic potential but still represents an under-studied topic.

Herein, we used NFI data and dense time series from the S2 mission to map the seven main tree species groups in the Netherlands and to compare map-based and NFI-based estimates of species area proportions. We used an RF model and evaluated different S2-based sets of predictors, including a new set of *harmonic predictors* which revealed greater performance compared to more standard seasonal composites. Then, estimates of forest species area proportions based on remote sensing-based maps were compared with those based on NFI data using an approach exploiting a grid of 10-km cells.

6.2. Map accuracies, harmonic predictors, and comparisons with other research

We aggregated species into seven main groups for species mapping in

Fig. 5. The omissions of models classifying conifers and broadleaf (top) and between species groups (bottom) using *harmonic predictors* (red), *medoid predictors* (green), and all predictors (blue). (For interpretation of the references to colour in this figure legend, the reader is referred to the web version of this article.)

Fig. 6. The commissions of models classifying conifers and broadleaf (top) and between species groups (bottom) using *harmonic predictors* (red), *medoid predictors* (green), and all predictors (blue). (For interpretation of the references to colour in this figure legend, the reader is referred to the web version of this article.)

Fig. 7. Forest species map with three focuses. Top left: reclaimed land in the Flevopolder, consisting of poplar plantations interspersed with oak stands and Other broadleaves. Top right: Detail of the Veluwe area in the province of Gelderland showing remnants of older oak and beech complexes, stands dark conifers on less degraded soils, and large areas of Scots pine afforestation on degraded poor soils. Bottom right: Noord-Brabant province, showing a smaller-scale pattern of Scots pine, Larix plantations, and remnants of oak coppices.

Table 2

Map accuracy and standard error estimates with 95% confidence intervals, calculated as detailed in Olofsson et al. (2014).

	Dark conifers	Fagus	Larix	Other broadleaves	Pines	Populus	Oak	Map accuracy (%)	CI (%)
Dark conifers	1448	56	83	26	227	11	119	73.5	± 2.0
Fagus	40	1804	20	22	31	17	36	91.6	± 1.3
Larix	76	18	1655	22	131	9	59	84.0	± 1.7
Other broadleaves	64	52	68	1410	28	97	251	71.6	± 2.0
Pines	152	10	79	10	1668	6	45	84.7	± 1.6
Populus	19	2	23	55	1	1833	37	93.0	± 1.1
Oak	56	110	89	89	83	65	1478	75.0	± 2.0
								80.2	± 1.7

the Netherlands. The grouping was initially based on the 20 groups defined by Schelhaas et al. (2018). Because distinguishing between very similar species using remotely sensed data is challenging, we merged all pines into one group, and conifers such as Norway spruce and Douglas fir into another group. Additionally, we merged the small remaining groups into the *Other broadleaves* species group. Overall, the models performed well at both the forest type (Table B.3) and species (Table B.6) levels. The within-cell proportions of species such as pines and *Other broadleaves* were consistently overestimated, while oak and larix proportions were often underestimated (Fig. 9). Accuracies within the various broadleaved species are relatively small, indicating that those species have similar spectral responses and, thus, are often confused with each other. The same applies to larch, which is often misclassified as a broadleaved species due to its phenological behavior. Still, the maps produce patterns that match well the known distributions

of species for different landscapes (Fig. 1).

In this study, we compared more traditional cloud-free seasonal composites (*medoid predictors*) against new time-series predictors designed to better capture differences in the phenological behavior of most species groups (*harmonic predictors*). The analysis of the variables' importance revealed that *medoid predictors* were generally and consistently less important than *harmonic predictors* (Figure A.6). This is even more clear when comparing the performance of models using *medoid* and *harmonic predictors* (Figs. 4, 5, and 6). Interestingly, in some cases, the model using both *harmonic* and *medoid predictors* was less accurate than the model that used exclusively *harmonic predictors*. Specifically, instead of increasing the accuracy, the addition of the *medoid predictors* increased *omissions* by 1% and 1.8% for the *Other broadleaves* and *larix* and *commissions* by 0.9%, 0.6%, and 0.2% for *quercus*, *larix*, and *fagus* species groups, respectively, pointing out the superiority of the *harmonic*

Fig. 8. Per-cell deviations (in proportion difference) between maps and NFI estimates.

predictors over the medoid predictors. Also, while in this study we focused on first-order harmonic functions, in future applications higher-order harmonic terms may be tested to obtain an even more fine representation of the pixel phenology and hopefully better predictors and consequently models with larger performance. Our results demonstrate the benefit of adding time series and phenological information in classifying tree species. Accordingly, [Zhu and Woodcock \(2014\)](#) demonstrated that the spectral phenological information of the dense S2 time series is suitable to map tree species over large areas accurately. The large potential of coupling Copernicus and NFI data for predicting tree species composition was also shown in several regions in Germany and Austria.

However, they concluded that a denser time series would be needed and NFI data were not an efficient reference dataset for nationwide tree species mapping due to the lack of location accuracy of the inventory field plots. [Blickensdörfer et al. \(2024\)](#) also mapped tree species in Germany by integrating NFI data with Sentinel-1 and S2 data and obtained large accuracies. On the other hand, they still reported consistent discrepancies between NFI-based and map-based estimates, especially for rare forest species, which are of key importance for forest biodiversity.

The reference data balancing step based on photointerpretation that we presented in this study ([section 4.2.1](#)) represents a valuable tool to

Fig. 9. Scatter plots and Pearson correlation coefficients between per-cell map estimates and NFI estimates. The dashed line indicates the expected relationship if both estimates agree perfectly. The solid line represents the actual relationship. Colors indicate the number of NFI plots in each cell.

refine NFI data and to integrate them with remotely sensed data. Similarly, the comparison procedure we described in [section 4.3](#) results in a powerful tool to properly compare and assess remote sensing-based estimates of forest species area proportions with NFI-based estimates.

Overall, Kollert et al. found that including phenological metrics produced an increase in OA of 1 to 2%. Accordingly, the OA in our study ranged between 90.5% – using exclusively *medoid predictors* – and 92.4% – using both *medoid* and *harmonic predictors*. The advantage of using *harmonic predictors* over *medoid predictors* was confirmed by all tests we performed, with greater evidence considering species groups: OA + 1.4% and kappa + 2.7% for the model predicting coniferous and broadleaves while OA + 7.3% and kappa + 8.6% for the model predicting species groups. *Omissions* were as great as –17% and *commissions* as great as –13%, depending on the species group. These results are encouraging and confirm important advantageous features in *harmonic predictors* compared to other studies on similar topics. For example, [Hermosilla et al. \(2022\)](#) mapped forest species over Canada using a Landsat annual composite ([White et al., 2014](#); [Hermosilla et al., 2015b](#); [Francini et al., 2023](#)) together with phenology data ([Bolton et al., 2020](#)) derived from Landsat and S2 imagery acquired between 2016 and 2019. [Hemmerling et al. \(2021\)](#) constructed and used model predictors based on 5-day, image-based cloud-free composites over two years. While they all used data over two or more years, we used data acquired over just one year (from 2019 to 11-15 to 2020-11-15). Constructing forest species maps using data acquired over different years can introduce some issues such as changes in species coverage or – most commonly – forest

disturbances. Also, considering large study areas, differences in phenological behavior are expected within the same species, considering data acquired over two different phenological seasons, mainly due to possible differences in the climate and weather conditions. The impact of these factors increases as the length of the time series increases and as the size of the study area increases ([Hemmerling et al., 2021](#)). In mountain areas and complex terrain, cloud cover can limit the number of valid observations available at the pixel level, definitely affecting the spatiotemporal patterns of the field reflectance and making it challenging to derive sound input variables. The yearly *harmonic predictors* presented herein may provide valuable solutions for large-scale forest species mapping, providing solid and consistent predictors capable of summarizing much information, mitigating the differences in the phenological behavior within the same species groups, and minimizing the effects of external factors such as disturbances, management activities, and climate conditions.

The potential of the *harmonic predictors* is confirmed by comparing the model performance we estimated with that of other reported research. For example, while [Hermosilla et al. \(2022\)](#) estimated an overall accuracy of 93%, they acknowledged that it was strongly driven by the dominance of black spruce forest species which represented 55% of the reference dataset. Accordingly, *omissions* were as great as 100% for some forest species and 34% on average, while *commissions* were as great as to 27% and 9% on average. Herein, we estimated comparable OA (92.4%) as a measure of model performance, but neither *omissions* nor *commissions* were ever greater than 28%, and both were 18% on

average. Considering map accuracy estimates (Table 2), OA was $80 \pm 2\%$ and the per-class *omissions* ranged between $7 \pm 1\%$ and $26 \pm 2\%$ and 18% on average. Although we merged Dutch forest species into seven main groups while they focused on 37 different species, the results we obtained are encouraging as all species groups are equally represented in our reference dataset, which was thus completely balanced.

Similar conclusions can be drawn by comparing our results with those obtained by Hemmerling et al. (2021). They used a very unbalanced reference dataset, with 85% of the sample points being Scots pine. While our model classified all species groups with *omissions* and *commissions* smaller than 28%, they classified some species with *omissions* as great as 90%, and more than half of the species with *commissions* greater than 50%. They achieved larger map OA than us (96% versus $80 \pm 2\%$), but the per-class accuracies of our map were very large, with *omissions* errors of 16% on average and 29% at most – for *Other broadleaves* species groups. Similar results were obtained in Denmark despite using Sentinel-1 predictors. They considered six dominant tree species and achieved tree species classification accuracies of 34 to 73% and forest type accuracies (broadleaf and conifer) of 96 and 95%, respectively. Importantly, while comparing the accuracies achieved in different studies is a noteworthy exercise, this comparison should be considered qualitative and not quantitative. Accordingly, these accuracies may change considerably depending on the dataset, the study area, and the validation procedure, and the reported differences are not necessarily due to differences in model performance nor in predictors efficiency.

6.3. Combining NFI and remote sensing-based forest species estimates

We aggregated and compared NFI and remote sensing-based estimates of forest species area proportions using a 10-km grid covering the whole of the Netherlands. Remarkably, the average deviation between map-based estimates and NFI estimates (Fig. 7) ranged between 0.2% for Oaks and 23% for *Other broadleaves*. This finding suggests that, despite originating from different datasets and methodologies, there is a noteworthy consistency between remote sensing-based and NFI-based estimates. Similar estimates can be produced for other crucial forest variables such as aboveground biomass (Vangi et al., 2023), forest area (Cavalli et al., 2022, 2023), or forest disturbance area estimates (Francini et al., 2022). However, in our study, direct estimation of forest species area proportions used the so-called “pixel counting” estimator. This estimator is known to be biased (Olofsson et al., 2014; Francini et al., 2021), because it does not account for map classification errors. Although scientific and technological advancements have substantially improved the accuracy of remotely sensed-based forest species maps, single-pixel predictions still remain susceptible to multiple errors (Olofsson et al., 2014; Marcelli et al., 2020). Conversely, NFI estimates also present limitations. For example, they are based on data collected over a minimal proportion of the whole study area and provide aggregated information just over large areas including at least 20–30 plots. Also, rare forest species are seldom observed in the field, possibly implying underestimations. Despite these inherent limitations in both NFI-based and remote sensing-based estimates, our study reveals a compelling methodological comparison and found a strong agreement between them, suggesting that remote sensing maps may play an essential role in complementing the information provided by NFIs. In the meantime, NFIs are still crucial as remote sensing-based forest species maps cannot be constructed without using reference data for model training (Blickensdörfer et al., 2024; Hermosilla et al., 2022; Hemmerling et al., 2021). In addition, we found that the deviations between remote sensing-based and NFI-based estimates were related to the number of NFI plots (Fig. 9). Excluding cells with fewer than 20 NFI plots reduced the average deviations to 0–11%. These results suggest that NFI plots might be insufficient to provide representative information over small areas and that in these cases remote sensing-based estimates may be exploited, being based on full-area sampling. Overall, both NFI-based and remote sensing-based approaches have strengths

and weaknesses for monitoring forest species across countries. Our forest species maps and estimates could serve as a valuable information source, particularly in regions with limited or inadequate data, thereby supplementing NFIs.

6.3.1. Issues and solutions

To improve the utility of NFI data for coupling with remotely sensed data, we identified homogenous areas around the NFI plots by photo-interpretation. By doing so, (i) we reduced the issues of plot position accuracy, (ii) we increased the numerosity of training data, (iii) we removed plots with changes in land cover, and (iv) we overcame the mismatch between the date of plot assessment and dates of image acquisition. However, some limitations in the training data persist, such as plots possibly located in a neighboring stand due to inaccurate coordinates, heterogeneous class of *Other broadleaves*, training on mono-species stands, and application to mixed stands. To address this last issue, mixture classes may be tested in future studies for machine learning model applications. Also, uncertainty in determining the main species in mixed stands both in the field and by photointerpretation may imply limitations in the training dataset. Several stands may not be homogenous enough for training models nor adequately predicted from remotely sensed data. The procedure we detailed in section 4.3 and summarized in Fig. 3 represents a powerful tool to produce information from NFI data to be combined with remote sensing-based information.

Overall, high-quality and reliable ground-truth data are indispensable for integration with earth observation techniques. Usually, NFIs are asked to deliver such data, because they have broad coverage across the country, are collected using sound and trusted methods, and are usually readily available. In practice, the usefulness of such data is hampered by the fact that most NFIs are unwilling to share the exact plot locations due to data integrity reasons and privacy issues. Similarly, plot coordinates can have large uncertainties, complicating the combination of NFI and remotely sensed data.

A fundamental prerequisite for building remote sensing-based models is the equitable representation of all species within the dataset. Some NFIs inherently do not satisfy this requirement. Stratified sampling using forest species maps to define the strata would increase the precision of the related estimates, but NFIs typically use some form of systematic sampling. Future efforts in species mapping should consider alternative methods of building a robust ground-truth dataset, with clear specifications for the information needed. One approach could be based on a subsample of the NFI data. Herein, we demonstrated a photointerpretation method for improving the capability of NFI data to be coupled with remote sensing, but we acknowledge that further effort may result in more reliable reference datasets. For example, in this study, we removed NFI plots for which the main recorded species on the plot had a basal area proportion smaller than 80%, which can imply an overestimation of the accuracy we calculated. Future research should aim at analyzing the relation between this threshold and the accuracy that can be reached, i.e., whether RS is capable of correctly classifying mixed stands.

Finally, our results suggest that – for this specific application – using remotely sensed data decreases the need for NFI data as it could decrease the number of plots to be visited in the field. However, we stress that such a decrease could severely affect the ability of the NFI to report on species that are less common and are not mapped explicitly but are included in broader groups, like rowan (*Sorbus aucuparia* L.) and *Other broadleaves*. Finally, the herein presented maps would be crucial to provide estimates for areas with insufficient information. This could, for example, be provinces with small forest cover and consequently an insufficient number of NFI plots or privately owned areas without a dedicated inventory. Our method may also help to predict forest conditions for NFI plots not visited during the field campaign. Importantly, the number of plots that could not be visited in NFI-7, either because of barriers (roads, fences, on islands, too wet terrain) or because the owners denied access, doubled since the previous inventory from 5% to

about 10% of the total number of plots.

7. Conclusions

This study led to four main scientific advancements.

First, we presented a set of remote sensing-based *harmonic predictors* that can be calculated from dense S2 time series and can help predict the pixel seasonality. Considering the seven species groups, these predictors increased the overall accuracy by 8% and the kappa coefficient by 9% while reducing omission and commission errors as much as 18% and 13%, respectively.

Second, we demonstrated a method to combine NFI and remotely sensed data to produce accurate forest species maps. We showed how to construct a useful training dataset through a photointerpretation step of the NFI data and how to address issues related to unbalanced datasets and mismatch of satellite and field data spatial and temporal resolutions.

Third, we developed a method to harmonize and compare forest species area proportions estimated from NFI and remotely sensed data. Accordingly, considering all species groups, we found that the average deviation between NFI-based and remote sensing-based estimates was 9%. In addition, the deviation between these estimates was large only in cells with very few NFI plots, suggesting that in these cells, NFI and remote sensing estimates may not be considered reliable. Our procedure can play an important role in understanding the relative strengths and limitations of remote sensing-based and NFI-based products, as well as be a useful basis for producing estimates when no field data are available.

Fourth, the herein detailed method constitutes an operational solution to integrate remote sensing and NFI data at the country level and to enhance NFI estimates. The resulting maps improve inventory estimates by providing spatially explicit estimates with a much greater level of detail (10-meter pixels) compared to those provided by NFIs, which are generated for municipalities or in general areas including at least 20–30 plots.

CRedit authorship contribution statement

Saverio Francini: Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Methodology, Formal analysis, Conceptualization. **Mart-Jan Schelhaas:** Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Methodology. **Elia Vangi:** Writing – review & editing, Data curation. **Bas**

Lerink: Writing – review & editing, Visualization. **Gert-Jan Nabuurs:** Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Conceptualization. **Ronald E. McRoberts:** Writing – review & editing, Methodology. **Gherardo Chirici:** Writing – review & editing, Supervision, Conceptualization.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

Data availability

Data will be made available on request.

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Appendix A. Predictors importance

Herein we present the results of the analysis of the variables’ importance, both for the broadleaves and conifers (Fig. A.1-3) and for the species groups models (Fig. A.4-6). Considering the model predicting conifers and broadleaves using just *medoid predictors* (Figure A.1), results indicate that all seasonal composites were more or less equally important, except for the redE3 and redE4 bands of the composite constructed using images acquired over summer (June-August), which were consistently more important than all other bands. Considering instead the model still predicting coniferous and broadleaves but using just *harmonic predictors* (Figure A.2), the most important predictors were the RMSE of EVI and NBR indices, strengthening the importance of photosynthetic activity indices when studying forest phenology over time. Finally, considering the model using both *medoid* and *harmonic predictors* (Figure A.3), most of the previous results were confirmed, with the redE3 and redE4 of summer composites being the most important *medoid predictors* and NBR root mean square error being the most important *harmonic predictor*.

As per the model predicting conifers and broadleaves, *medoid predictors*’ importance was similar for all seasonal composites, with values slightly smaller in winter (Figure A.4). Also, no relevant differences were recorded looking at the model using *harmonic predictors* (Figure A.5). Finally, when considering the model predicting species groups and not just conifers and broadleaves, *medoid predictors* importance was generally consistently smaller than that of *harmonic predictors* (Figure A.6).

Fig. A1. Predictors importance of the model using medoid predictors for classifying between coniferous and broadleaves. Predictors in the chart have the same order as predictors in the legend.

Fig. A2. Predictors importance of model using *harmonic predictors* for classifying between coniferous and broadleaves. Predictors in the chart have the same order as predictors in the legend.

Fig. A3. Predictors importance of model using all predictors for classifying between coniferous and broadleaves Predictors in the chart have the same order as predictors in the legend.

Fig. A4. Predictors importance of model using medoid predictors for classifying species groups. Predictors in the chart have the same order as predictors in the legend.

Fig. A5. Predictors importance of model using harmonic predictors for classifying species groups. Predictors in the chart have the same order as predictors in the legend.

Fig. A6. Predictors importance of model using all predictors for classifying species groups. Predictors in the chart have the same order as predictors in the legend.

Appendix B. Confusion matrices

Table B1

Confusion matrix of the model using medoid predictors for classifying between coniferous and broadleaves.

	Broadleaves	Conifer	Producer accuracy
Broadleaves	7292	588	0.93
Conifer	720	5190	0.88
User accuracy	0.91	0.90	OA = 0.91

Table B2

Confusion matrix of model using harmonic predictors for classifying between coniferous and broadleaves.

	Broadleaves	Conifer	Producer accuracy
Broadleaves	7390	490	0.94
Conifer	632	5278	0.89
User accuracy	0.92	0.92	OA = 0.92

Table B3

Confusion matrix of model using all predictors for classifying between coniferous and broadleaves.

	Broadleaves	Conifer	Producer accuracy
Broadleaves	7431	449	0.94
Conifer	593	5317	0.90
User accuracy	0.93	0.92	OA = 0.92

Table B4

Confusion matrix of model using medoid predictors for classifying species groups.

	Dark conifers	Fagus	Larix	Other broadleaves	Pines	Populus	Oak	Producer accuracy
Dark conifers	1289	89	147	34	273	15	123	0.65
Fagus	75	1664	56	30	42	27	76	0.84
Larix	198	81	1350	22	200	15	104	0.69
Other broadleaves	63	83	69	1311	38	178	228	0.67
Pines	169	16	152	10	1570	8	45	0.80
Populus	17	3	32	98	4	1745	71	0.89
Oak	86	182	124	113	86	120	1259	0.64
User accuracy	0.68	0.79	0.70	0.81	0.71	0.83	0.66	OA = 0.74

Table B5

Confusion matrix of model using harmonic predictors for classifying species groups.

	Dark conifers	Fagus	Larix	Other broadleaves	Pines	Populus	Oak	Producer accuracy
Dark conifers	1419	41	81	51	255	8	115	0.72
Fagus	38	1771	22	34	39	14	52	0.90
Larix	61	13	1690	35	102	16	53	0.86
Other broadleaves	63	62	72	1431	42	97	203	0.73
Pines	220	12	61	6	1618	7	46	0.82
Populus	22	12	33	43	3	1810	47	0.92
Oak	80	99	85	92	89	67	1458	0.74
User accuracy	0.75	0.88	0.83	0.85	0.75	0.90	0.74	OA = 0.81

Table B6

Confusion matrix of model using all predictors for classifying species group & map accuracy estimation (Olofsson et al., 2014). #pixels column indicates the number of pixels that were classified as that specific class in the map. Weight is the proportion of the map in that class. 0.80, or 80%, is the estimate of the map overall accuracy. CI(%) are the 95% confidence interval of the class accuracy estimates in percentage, and 1.74 is the confidence interval of the overall accuracy estimate.

	Dark conifers	Fagus	Larix	Other broadleaves	Pines	Populus	Oak	Tot	Producer Accuracy (%)	#pixels	weight	Weight × Acc	var	CI (%)	Weight × CI
Dark conifers	1448	56	83	26	227	11	119	1970	73	1,876,034	0.13	0.09	0.00010	1.99	0.25
Fagus	40	1804	20	22	31	17	36	1970	91	658,953	0.04	0.04	0.00004	1.25	0.06
Larix	76	18	1655	22	131	9	59	1970	84	1,544,282	0.10	0.09	0.00007	1.65	0.17
Other broadleaves	64	52	68	1410	28	97	251	1970	71	1,770,428	0.12	0.08	0.00010	2.03	0.24
Pines	152	10	79	10	1668	6	45	1970	84	3,553,418	0.24	0.20	0.00007	1.62	0.39
Populus	19	2	23	55	1	1833	37	1970	93	1,507,324	0.10	0.09	0.00003	1.15	0.12
Oak	56	110	89	89	83	65	1478	1970	75	4,021,271	0.27	0.20	0.00010	1.95	0.53
Tot	1855	2052	2017	1634	2169	2038	2025	13,790		14,931,710	1.00	Map OA = 0.80			1.74
User Accuracy	0.781	0.879	0.821	0.863	0.769	0.899	0.730		Model OA = 0.82						

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